

INDIVIDUAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: *This study provides information about the main essence of the psychological effects of individual characteristics on the development of the individual. It also analyzes the well-founded opinions and ideas of scientists about the characteristics of individuality in the development of the individual. During the study, information is provided about the influence of the psychological environment on the development of the individual and the main characteristics of individuality.*

Keywords: *Personality, psychological approach, individuality, personal development, upbringing, socio-psychological environment, personal development.*

SHAXS RIVOJLANISHINING INDIVIDUALLIK XUSUSIYATLARI

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu tadqiqotda shaxs rivojlanishining individuallik xususiyatlarining psixologik ta'sirlarining asosiy mohiyati haqida ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tilgan. Shuningdek olimlarning shaxsning rivojlanishida individuallik xususiyatlari haqidagi asoslangan mulohazalari va fikrlari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot davomida shaxs rivojlanishida psixologik muhitning ta'siri va individuallikning asosiy xususiyatlari haqida ma'lumotlar beriladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Shaxs, psixologik yondashuv, individuallik, shaxs komoloti, tarbiya, ijtimoiy-psixologik muhit, shaxs rivojlanishi.*

ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ЛИЧНОСТИ

Аннотация. *В настоящем исследовании представлена информация об основной сути психологического влияния индивидуальных особенностей на развитие личности. Анализируются также обоснованные мнения и идеи ученых об особенностях индивидуальности в развитии личности. Исследование предоставляет информацию о влиянии психологической среды на развитие личности и основные характеристики индивидуальности.*

Ключевые слова: Личность, психологический подход, индивидуальность, личностное развитие, воспитание, социально-психологическая среда, личностное развитие.

Introduction

The concept of personality refers to a person and serves to express a member of society who is psychologically developed, distinguished from others by his personal characteristics and actions, and has a certain behavior and worldview. In order to be a person, a person must develop psychologically, feel himself as a whole person, and differ from others with his own characteristics and qualities. In the national model of personnel training, a person is defined as the main subject and object of the personnel training system, a consumer of educational services and their implementer. Personal development. In order for a person to become a person as a social being, social environmental conditions and upbringing are necessary. Under the influence of these, a person develops as a person and becomes a person. Development is a complex process that expresses the essence of quantitative and qualitative changes that are manifested in the physiological and intellectual growth of a person. The problem of the structure of the personality goes beyond the scope of its research. The creation and development of scientific ideas about the structure of the personality is considered a necessary condition for a holistic theory and has the ability to reveal the facets of the social essence of man. For this reason, the fact that representatives of such disciplines as philosophy, pedagogy, and medicine express different opinions on psychology and its interpretation is a vivid example of this. It is a legitimate fact that the most significant scientific research on the structural approach to the personality has been carried out in psychology, and the creation of a diverse model of the structure of the personality is a vivid proof of our opinion. According to B.G. Anan'ev, the process of dividing psychological phenomena into intelligence (intellect), feelings (emotions), and will is the initial manifestation of the experience of the structural approach in human psychology, and its correctness has been recognized by many psychologists. According to L.S. Vygotsky, human psychic functions can be divided into higher, cultural and lower, natural types. Because at their core lies the expression of the interaction between education and the first and second signal systems in the higher nervous activity of a person. The main reason for the significant difficulty in developing a model of personality structure is manifested in the existence of different points of view. They are based on the research of V.M. Banishikov, who considers the structure of the personality to have substantial and ideal, hereditary and

psychological aspects. It is clear from the analysis that in this case the “substantial side” of the personality, in comparison with the somatic aspects that occupy it in everyday life, as an independent structural component, does not have any reality. Such an analysis indicates that we are talking about individual reality. According to A.G. Kovalev, temperament expresses the importance of natural characteristics. Development is essentially a transition from simple to complex, from bottom to top, from old qualities to new states, renewal, the emergence of the new, the disappearance of the old, the transition of quantitative changes to qualitative changes. The source of development is the struggle between contradictions. The development of a child's personality is based on the philosophical teaching that man is a social being. At the same time, man is also a living, biological being. Therefore, the laws of natural development are also important in its development. Also, since a person is considered as a whole being, his development is influenced by biological and social laws together, they cannot be separated from each other. Because a person's activity and lifestyle are affected by age, knowledge, life experience, as well as other tragic circumstances and diseases. A person changes throughout his life. He matures both socially and psychologically, and if the upbringing given to the child is appropriate, he will mature as a member of society and take his rightful place in the complex system of social relations. Because development occurs under the influence of upbringing. In order to correctly see and accurately assess the qualities of a person, it is necessary to observe him in the process of various relationships. Therefore, in order to correctly solve the task of developing a person, it is necessary to know well the factors affecting his behavior and personal characteristics. In order for upbringing to effectively affect the child, it is advisable to know and take into account the laws of growth and development. Thus, there is a two-way relationship between development and upbringing. Education is a practical pedagogical process aimed at forming certain physical, mental, moral, and spiritual qualities in a person; a set of measures taken to ensure that a person has the characteristics necessary for living in society. Education is the most ancient and eternal value that ensures human humanity. Without education, neither an individual nor a human society can exist. Because the values that ensure the existence of a person and society are passed on from one generation to another only thanks to education. In pedagogical literature, the term "Education" is used in broad and narrow meanings. In a broad sense, education means the sum of all influences, activities, actions, and aspirations aimed at forming a human personality, ensuring its active participation in the production and social, cultural, and educational life of society. In this understanding, upbringing includes not only educational work carried out in the family, school, children's and youth organizations, but also

the entire social system, its leading ideas, literature, art, cinema, radio, television, etc. Also, the concept of upbringing in a broad sense includes education and information. In a narrow sense, education means pedagogical activity aimed at the development of the physical development of the individual, his worldview, spiritual and moral image, aesthetic taste. The main category of personality orientation is need. Based on psychological sources, in our thinking, need is expressed as a state that expresses the subjection of a living being and demonstrates its activity in relation to these conditions. When considering existence from a psychological point of view, the activity of living beings (from simple to complex) that provides vital connections with the environment of various characteristics (regardless of their level and form) is a common feature for all of them. Due to their activity, complex structured activity arises, and as a product of consciousness, needs of various essences and various forms serve to satisfy biological, material, spiritual, etc. in terms of their origin and affiliation to categories. For this reason, activity is one of the main mechanisms of activity and is considered a component of the ability of living beings to respond to the influences of the external world to the best of their ability. Individuality is a specific thing and phenomenon, a person and an animal, which have their own, unique, private characteristics. Individuality is contrasted with generality (and the individual with the general) by the uniqueness of the qualities of the sign. Initially, individuality was known in antiquity by the prominent Greek philosophers Leucippus and Democritus in the process of identifying the characteristics inherent in things and phenomena that have a specific form and content, that is, specific signs, including the atom or individual (i.e., indivisible). The ancient Roman philosopher Seneca further improved the concept of individuality. He recognized that individuality is a specific thing (being) that cannot be divided into other parts, without losing its specific characteristics and content. In medieval philosophy, individuality represented the concept of the human person. In the XVII century, ideas related to individuality were comprehensively developed in the teachings of the German philosopher Leibniz. Individuality also found its expression in the works of the German writer I. V. Goethe. Individuality is also a characteristic feature of the romantic worldview. Individuality in a person is considered to be his unique qualities that are manifested in all areas of his life and activity. Individuality, taken separately, expresses the specific behavior, skills, abilities, habits and skills of a person. It differs from others because of the formation of unique internal and external characteristics of a person. It includes character, temperament, will, talents, abilities, etc., and they are not repeated. That is, the talents, abilities, emotions, facial expressions, and characters that are characteristic of one person are not found in another person exactly. For this reason, they are individual.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that in the development of a person, based on the main psychological aspects of the individual's character, the spiritual growth and mental health of the person are inextricably linked to his educational status. Based on the individual's status, the main characteristics of psychological influences play an important role in the development of the person.

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